

METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES - RECENT ADVANCES

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In the last decade, there has been a dramatic increase in the potential applications of metal matrix composites (MMC) for both defense and commercial sectors. The success of MMC can be attributed to recent technical advances in analytical modeling, reinforcements and economical processing techniques, which have resulted in improved reliability and reduced production cost. Still, the fundamental knowledge of composite behavior, such as interface structures and its effect on material properties, has to be expanded in order to optimize the design and fabrication of MMC. Two significant areas (1) structure and property of interfaces, and (2) advances in casting technology, are reviewed in this paper.

FIBER - MATRIX INTERFACES

The historical approach to developing structural composites has emphasized primarily the properties and architectural arrangement of reinforcing fibers, with the matrix being of secondary importance. Little attention has been paid to fiber-matrix interfaces which are zones of compositional, structural, and property gradients. Because of their chemical and microstructural complexities, kinetics, thermodynamics, mechanics, etc. of processes occurring at interfaces are not well understood. In particular, the mechanical properties of interfaces, especially their fracture mechanics, were ill determined. Recently, new theoretical and experimental tools have been developed which have made possible major advances in our understanding of interfaces [1]. The three primary mechanical phenomena of interest at interfaces are fiber-matrix debonding, frictional sliding along debonded

regions and residual stress state.

Fiber-Matrix Debonding In an analysis of the fracture behavior of brittle materials, enhancement of toughness was attributed to the interference between the primary cracks and fine cracks which were often along the weak planes, perpendicular to the direction of crack propagation [2]. To describe the fracture toughness in homogeneous materials, only one parameter, the critical stress intensity factor, K_{IC} , is needed. In contrast, a more complex fracture mechanics theory is required for composites because of their anisotropy and the presence of interfaces. Also, complexities arise from shearing of the crack surfaces due to the modulus mismatch. In such a situation, the parameter K is scale sensitive [3]. However, the critical strain energy release rate, G_{IC} , is not, and is therefore, a convenient parameter to describe the debonding process [4]. G is, however, a function of the complex phase angle, ϕ , which is a measure of the extent of normal and shear loading [5]. Consequently, one must specify both G and ϕ when describing interfacial debonding. Fig. 1 shows a schematic of crack propagating along a bimaterial (equivalently fiber-matrix) interface. Because of elastic mismatch, a degree of rotation is superimposed upon a stress state which is caused by a remotely applied, purely tensile load. The phase angle, ϕ , can be expressed in terms of the rotational displacement and elastic coefficients. The elastic coefficients can be arranged in terms of two (rather than three) dimensionless expressions called the Dundurs parameters, α , [6]. One can determine values of stress intensity factors, K , directly from G . As shown in Fig. 2, these concepts have been used to establish criteria for the maximum interfacial toughness that is consistent with interfacial debonding [5]. The figure shows correlation of the ratio of interfacial to fiber toughness (or strain energy release rate) to elastic mismatch as expressed by the Dundurs parameter. For the case in which the mismatch is zero, the interfacial toughness must be less than 1/4 that of the fiber in order for the fiber and matrix to debond. Otherwise, the crack will propagate into the fiber. For values of elastic mismatch greater than zero, the minimum interfacial toughness for debonding increases. The conclusion is that high modulus fibers promote debonding.

Using analytical and finite element solutions, a specimen has been designed [7] to describe interfacial debonding under conditions of known phase angle, ϕ . Fig. 3 shows a schematic of the bimaterial flexure specimen in which a precrack at the notch root is initiated along the fiber matrix interface. During four point flexure loading, the normal and shear components are approximately equal, and the phase angle is about forty-five degrees. One can determine G , and consequently K , directly from the load at which the interfacial crack begins to propagate, and the specimen dimensions.

Micromechanical modeling of crack-tip fields at interfaces has also been performed to generate a relationship between the Dundurs parameter, α , and the ratio of interface

cohesive strength to fiber fracture strength. Using these relationships, and a knowledge of the compliances of interphases of matrices and reinforcements, one can determine the maximum cohesive interfacial strength which will permit delamination.

A particularly useful experimental technique for correlating interface cohesive strength with processing parameters has been developed which uses a laser induced pressure pulse to promote interfacial separation [8]. The method, illustrated schematically in Fig. 4, consists of the use of a finite element simulation of the conversion of a laser light pulse into a pressure pulse based on the simultaneous solution of the transient heat transfer and elastic pressure wave generation problems. The pressure pulse is correlated with laser fluence and the predictions of the computer simulation checked by calibrating the system with an X-cut piezo-electric crystal. Finally, actual spallation experiments are carried out on substrates and coatings of interest, and the cohesive strength determined from the laser fluence necessary to accomplish spallation.

Fiber-Matrix Sliding As discussed above, the other aspect of the debonding analysis during fiber-matrix interfacial cracking involves consideration of interfacial sliding between the fiber and matrix. The schematic in Fig. 5 presents the results of a model for the process by which toughening is achieved, in a brittle matrix composite, due to energy absorption during the frictional sliding and pullout of broken fibers [9]. Consequently, it is of great interest to quantify interfacial frictional sliding stresses.

Fiber depression or push-out techniques are being used to quantify the mechanical properties of interfaces undergoing frictional sliding. Usually the techniques involve loading a fiber with a miniature indenter and simultaneously measuring load and fiber displacement as shown schematically in Fig. 6. Of particular interest in such investigations, is the presence of chemical bonding between fiber and matrix, the relative values of static and dynamic friction stresses, and whether there is any variation in frictional stress along the length of the fiber. One such technique which involves application of a load by a coil and magnet assembly and measurement of displacement with a capacitance gage, achieves load and displacement resolutions of 0.5 micronewton and two angstroms, respectively [10]. The investigators used a micromechanical analysis which takes into account the distribution of axial strain along the fiber. From the data, the frictional sliding stress and the magnitude of the debond shear strength can be determined.

Residual Stress State Fiber depression methods can also be used to quantify residual stresses resulting from differential contraction of the fibers and matrix during cooling from the composite fabrication temperature. Such stresses are notoriously difficult to measure. The micromechanical analysis has been modified to include the effect of residual stresses

on the force-displacement relation for sliding between a fiber and matrix [11]. The force-displacement relations for the first loading and unloading cycle of a fiber reinforced composite are influenced by the presence of residual tensile and compressive stresses within the matrix and fiber, respectively. Fig. 6 illustrates that the presence of the residual stresses causes nonlinearity in the initial loading curves (positive curvature for residual tension and negative for residual compression) and also affects the amount of recovery when the fiber is unloaded as compared to the case of no residual stresses.

In addition, acoustic emission techniques have also been used to determine the magnitude of residual stresses in continuously reinforced MMC [12]. During tensile loading, a two peak r.m.s. behavior was observed in Gr/Al and Gr/Mg specimens, the low amplitude peak being attributed to matrix yielding and interfacial degradation, while the high amplitude peak was due to fiber breakage (Fig. 7). Detection of the onset of matrix yielding in graphite-aluminum composites by acoustic emission techniques was used to determine the magnitude of residual stresses. Using this approach, residual stresses in diffusion bonded [0°] Pitch-55/6061 aluminum composite was found to be between 35.2 and 124.8 MPa (5.1 and 18.1 klb/in²), depending upon whether the aluminum alloy 6061 matrix when incorporated in the composite was in the 0 or T4 condition. Similar techniques for cast graphite-Mg composites indicated much lower levels of residual stress of 24.6 MPa (3.53 klb/in²).

CASTING TECHNOLOGIES

Once the role of interfaces on composite behavior is fully understood, the challenge is to develop and control fabrication processes to achieve the designed interface. Casting of MMC has been one of the important processing methods which is both economical and has great potential to control interfacial properties. To develop good casting processes, two important phenomenons have to be systematically studied: (1) fiber wetting, and (2) matrix infiltration.

Fiber Wetting Wettability of a fiber by molten metal is indicated by the contact angle θ defined in Figure 8, which is related to the surface tensions γ_{FA} , γ_{FL} , and γ_{LA} of the interfaces: fiber (F)-air (A), fiber-liquid (L), and liquid-air, respectively. For equilibrium

$$\gamma_{LA} \cos \theta = \gamma_{FA} - \gamma_{FL} \quad (1)$$

For spontaneous wetting the contact angle is less than 90°, i.e., $\cos \theta > 0$

$$\text{or } \gamma_{FA} - \gamma_{FL} > 0 \quad \text{or } \gamma_{FA} > \gamma_{FL}$$

Matrix Infiltration The infiltration of liquid into a fiber network can be modeled by assuming that the network is made of cylindrical capillaries of radius r , into which the liquid has to infiltrate. Fig. 9 schematically describes a liquid-air interface across a

capillary. In the absence of chemical interaction between the fiber and liquid, the minimum infiltration pressure, ΔP_I , necessary to move the infiltration front and the interface isothermally along the capillary, can be calculated by knowing the change in free energy of the system, and defined as:

$$\Delta P_I \geq -2\gamma_{LA} \cos\theta/r \quad (2)$$

Thus Equation [2] determines the magnitude of the applied pressure, ΔP_I , needed to infiltrate the smallest capillary of radius r .

Both the interfiber spacing and wetting conditions encountered by the advancing fiber-liquid interface significantly influence the infiltration pressure. The calculated values of infiltration pressure for wetting ($\theta \leq 90^\circ$) and nonwetting ($\theta > 90^\circ$) conditions, as a function of different intercapillary sizes, are shown in Figure 10 for the Gr/Mg system. For $\theta > 90^\circ$, the infiltration pressures are positive for all interfiber spacing, whereas for $\theta \leq 90^\circ$, the infiltration pressures are negative; the case of spontaneous wetting.

In a nonwetting case, the interface bonding can arise from mechanical interlocking or from frictional effects arising from the contraction of matrix on the fiber. The reinforcing fiber network probably consists of a series of bottlenecks through which the liquid has to penetrate. Under an applied pressure ΔP_a or $\Delta P_{\text{feeding}}$, the distance, x , travelled by the liquid of viscosity, η , into the capillary of radius, r , after a time, t , can be computed using the following expression [13]:

$$x = [r^2 \cdot t / 4\eta (\Delta P_a - 2\gamma_{LA} \cos \theta)/r]^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

Normally the molten metal does not wet the ceramic fiber and the infiltration into narrow interfiber spacing becomes difficult because typical feeding pressures are less than the required infiltration pressures. Whereas, if the wetting conditions (i.e., $\theta \leq 90^\circ$) can be generated between molten metal and ceramic fiber, the feeding pressure will always exceed the infiltration pressure and promote matrix infiltration along the interfiber capillaries. For example, applying a surface coating such as SiO_2/SiC on graphite fibers the contact angle can be varied to attain favorable wetting conditions with molten Mg. In addition, the chemical reactions between the matrix (Mg) and SiO_2 coating described below may also improve wettability.

The characterization of the interface structure in Gr/Mg composites by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) confirms that magnesium silicide (Mg_2Si) and magnesium oxide (MgO) precipitates are formed during the chemical reactions [14] as shown in Fig. 11. The chemical reactions between the coated

Gr fiber and Mg matrix must occur to achieve good wetting and matrix infiltration.

Continuously Reinforced MMC: Based on the fundamental understanding of fiber wettability and matrix infiltration, casting techniques have been developed to produce Gr/Mg and Gr/Al components. The infiltration of molten metal into the fiber network can be initiated when the feeding pressure is greater than the infiltration pressure

$$\text{i.e., } \Delta P_{\text{feeding}} > \Delta P_{\text{infiltration}} (\Delta P_1) \quad (5)$$

In continuous fiber reinforced casting, applications of pressure has been a difficult task. For the wetting situation (w/SiO₂ coating), such as Gr/Mg, application of vacuum (10⁻³ Torr) has been enough to provide the needed ΔP_1 with complete infiltration. However, in the absence of surface coating, i.e., the nonwetting case, the process does not work.

One method to apply the needed pressure is centrifugal casting where the molten metal is introduced into a mold rotating about its own axis and the bore shape is produced by the centrifugal force.

The centrifugal force (F_c) acting on the metal inside a rotating mold is the product of the mass (m), the radius (R), and the square of the angular velocity (ω):

$$F_c = mR\omega^2 = mR\pi^2N^2/900 \text{ since } \omega = \frac{2\pi N}{60} \quad (6)$$

where N is the rotational speed (rpm).

The feeding pressure (ΔP) (i.e., centrifugal force) provided by the rotation of the mold is given by the Equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta P_{\text{feeding}} &= \rho\omega^2 (R_2^2 - R_1^2)/2 \\ \Delta P_{\text{feeding}} &= \rho \cdot \pi^2N^2(R_2^2 - R_1^2)/1800, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where ρ is the density, R_1 is the bore radius (i.e., cast tube ID), and R_2 is the radius of rotation at the point where the feeding pressure is to be calculated. For the matrix infiltration centrifugal force should be greater than infiltration pressure, i.e.,

$$\rho \cdot \pi^2N^2(R_2^2 - R_1^2)/1800 \geq - 2 \gamma_{LA} \cos \theta/r. \quad (8)$$

This inequality can be used to describe the optimum combination of process parameters (R_1 , R_2 , and N) required for nonwetting and wetting condition. Based on the above analysis of the centrifugal and infiltration process, optimum thermal, chemical and mechanical conditions were identified and Gr/Al and Gr/Mg tubes were successfully produced by Martin Marietta Defense Space and Communications Company [15]. In practice, high-feeding pressures can be attained in centrifugal casting process using an optimum combinations of R_1 , R_2 , and N that can facilitate matrix infiltration into a fiber preform.

Discontinuously Reinforced MMC

Recently significant advancements have been made in the casting technology of discontinuously reinforced MMC. The Duralcan process [16] where particles are injected into molten metal and the mixture solidified. A remarkable attribute of the process is the recastability of Duralcan billets into near net shape components using conventional casting practices. Semi-solid slurry casting [17] and pressure assist casting [18, 19] processes have been successful to incorporate higher volume fraction and improved properties over Duralcan material but at higher production cost. Lanxide™ [20] has developed a pressureless infiltration process, and they can achieve extremely high volume fraction with up to 60% for high performance components.

Normally, discontinuous reinforced MMC's are more difficult to cast due to their inherent high viscosity especially if the volume fraction exceeds 15%. In addition, the solidification kinetics becomes more complicated due to the particle rich liquid and the movement of the particles in the solidifying liquid. The movement of particles during solidification and their distribution after solidification can be best studied by centrifugal casting experiments. The different forces on the particle, i.e., centrifugal, viscous and gravitational, are schematically shown in Fig. 12. Ignoring gravitational forces since $\omega^2 r \gg g$, the force balance equation can be expressed as follows:

$$\frac{4}{3} \pi R_p^3 \rho_p \frac{d^2 r}{dt^2} = \frac{4}{3} \pi R_p^3 \omega^2 \cdot r (\rho_p - \rho_L) - 6\pi \eta_L R_p \frac{dr}{dt} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{i.e.,} \quad r = r_0 \exp \left(\frac{2\omega^2 (\rho_p - \rho_L) \cdot R_p^2 \cdot t}{9\eta_L} \right) \quad (10)$$

where R_p = Particle radius, ρ_p = density of particle, r = position of the particle at time t , ω = angular rotational velocity of mold, η_L = viscosity of the liquid alloy, ρ_L = density of the liquid alloy

The equation [10] combined with the thermal conditions provides the location and distribution of the particles in the casting based on their size and density. One such analytical distribution curve for SiC_p in the aluminum matrix is shown in Fig. 13 [21, 22]. The experiments conducted at Martin Marietta [22] with carbon microballoon/flakes (density 0.98 gm/cc), and SiC (3.15 gm/cc) show good agreement with the predicted distribution, as shown in Fig. 14. In this hybrid composite, low density carbon microballoon/flakes segregated near the internal diameter and high density SiC_p particles segregated near the outer region.

CONCLUSION

In order to optimize the performance of metal matrix composites, it is essential to fundamentally understand the structure and property of reinforcement and matrix interfaces. With the micromechanical and experimental tools now available, material scientists have abilities to predict and quantify interfacial properties necessary to achieve the optimum composite behavior. However, the challenge is to develop understanding and control of the fabrication processes such as casting in order to create interfacial chemistry and microstructure which will achieve these properties.

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Fig. 1 Displacement of crack surface at interface

Fig. 2 Conditions for interface debonding in terms of strain energy release rate

Fig. 3 Schematic of test specimen for measurement of interface fracture resistance under mixed mode loading

Fig. 4 Laser spallation experiment

Fig. 5 Schematic of fractional sliding and pullout in fiber-reinforced composite

Fig. 6 Fiber depression technique for quantifying sliding properties of interfaces

Fig. 7 Stress-strain and r.m.s. behavior of four-ply [0°] P-55 Gr-Al 6061 displaying a slight r.m.s. lift-off and the presence of an r.m.s. peak beginning at 8 klbf in² stress

Fig. 8 Schematic Illustrating the Wettability of Molten Droplet on the Graphite Fiber Surface

Fig. 9 Schematic illustrating the infiltration of molten magnesium into inter Gr fiber capillaries of radius, r

* psi = 6.89 KPa

Fig. 10 Calculated pressure for infiltration of molten magnesium into graphite fiber tows as a function of interfiber capillary for wetting and nonwetting conditions

Fig. 11 Blocky precipitate at the fiber-matrix interface in cast Gr/Mg showing evidence of faceting, typical of large single crystal grain structures. The inset electron diffraction pattern obtained from the block precipitate confirms it is a cubic Mg₂Si precipitate

Fig. 12 Schematic showing forces influencing the movement of a particle suspended in molten liquid during centrifugal motion

Fig. 13 Particle segregation in centrifugally cast SiC_p/Al-theory and experiment

Fig. 14 Particle segregation in carbon microballoon/flake - SiC_p/Al composite